

Navigating TechCentral's Ecosystem: A Role for Transport

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663
Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and
Initiating Change, 2021 cohort

Courtney Brennan, Szymon Glewicz, Zhikang Lai, Tiangyun Pan, Sofia Styles, and Ryan Yii

September 2021

About TD School

TD School (ex Faculty of Transdisciplinary Innovation) is a new pan-university School at UTS, established in 2017 as a nexus for transdisciplinary thought and practice. The UTS TD School is on a mission to instigate a monumental, revolutionary change to tertiary education and research through transdisciplinary innovation. We believe the complex problems we're facing in the world require solutions that transdisciplinary thinking can provide. The first of its kind in Australia, our school brings together great minds from different disciplines to explore ideas that improve the way we live and work in the world.

For further information visit: www.uts.edu.au/about/td-school

Team

**Courtney Brennan, Szymon Glewicz,
Zhikang Lai, Tianyun Pan, Sofia Styles, and
Ryan Yii**

Citation

Please cite as: Brennan, C., Glewicz, S., Lai, Z., Pan, T., Styles, S., and Yii, R. 2021, Navigating TechCentral's Ecosystem: A Role for Transport. Report by coursework students of UTS 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, 2021 cohort

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.5344944

Subject Coordination

Assoc. Prof Martin Bliemel
Course Director (Diploma in Innovation)
Director, Research
UTS: TD School

Yara Vasina
Tutor, 94663 Navigating Ecosystems
UTS: TD School

Foreword

This report is part of a series of student generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework, conducted in collaboration with multiple industry partners and interviews with stakeholders in the ecosystem. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws directly on Martin's prior experience in visualising entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals that will bring the ecosystem forward.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

Methodology

The cohort of 50+ students was divided into random teams, each of which could choose their own ecosystem to focus on, with the only caveat being that it relates to TechCentral. Generally, the ecosystems were geographically in the immediate vicinity of TechCentral³, but varied significantly in terms of their sectoral focus.

Each team was instructed to consider the types of stakeholder based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,⁴ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE). Teams adopt a qualitative approach, involving interviewing a broad range of participants to extract insights on their interpersonal connections and interrelations between factors and to identify specific opportunities for change. Each participant is believed to have a clear view of their immediate ecosystem, from which teams stitch together the more holistic view of how the ecosystem works.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

Acknowledgements

The subject coordination team would like to acknowledge the contributions by guests of the July 2021 cohort of 94663, especially Murray Hurps (UTS Startups), Neville Stevens AO (NSW Innovation and Productivity Council), Michelle Long (Sydney Startup Hub), and Peter Davison (co-Founder of Fishburners).

¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.uts.edu.au/news/innovation/welcome-neighbourhood-tech-central>

⁴ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

Contents

Foreword	3
Methodology	3
Acknowledgements	3
1 Ecosystem Evolution	5
1.1 City of Sydney Local Government Area	5
1.2 Transportation	5
1.3 Education	6
2 Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Map	7
2.1 Important Ecosystem Factors	8
2.1.1 Leadership & Council	8
2.1.2 Education	8
2.1.3 Talent & Knowledge	8
2.1.4 Support Services	8
2.1.5 Sustainability	8
2.1.6 Networks/Culture & Infrastructure	8
2.1.7 Finance	9
3 Leverage Proposal	9
3.1 Vision for Proposal	9
3.2 Opportunities for development in the EE	9
3.3 Relevant Stakeholder Interactions	9
3.3.1 Transport NSW	9
3.3.2 Entrepreneurs	10
3.3.3 STEM Students	10
3.3.4 Tech Central	10
3.4 Execution of proposal - How will it work?	10
3.5 Projections of the EE	11
References	12

1 Ecosystem Evolution

The Transport industry in the City of Sydney area is home to various stakeholders, all which link to the broader entrepreneurial ecosystem. The evolution of its local government area and changes to its regulations and policies has shaped its overall development to being the central hub for both transport, innovation and entrepreneurial ecosystems. The timeline below highlights the engagement of individual players within the area to form much needed resources such as transport hubs, innovation centres and government infrastructure, all of which are valuable to facilitate innovative and entrepreneurial growth.

1.1 City of Sydney Local Government Area

The "City of Sydney" was established on July 20, 1842 by the Corporation Act which encompasses present-day Woolloomooloo, Surry Hills, Chippendale and Pyrmont, an area of

11.65 km². Today that area has grown to include surrounding CBD suburbs, and now covers a 25km² area. In 1982, South Sydney was brought back into the city but became independent again under the City of Sydney Act of 1988. The City of Sydney Act 1988 (NSW) was then established and updated by the NSW government to define and regulate the election and voting for the City of Sydney Council, constitute committees for sustainable development and set up planning provisions relating to the City Council.

The City of Sydney has adopted various policies to reduce the council's climate impact, including strategies implemented since the 2000s to reduce car pollution by investing in mass and public transit and introducing a fleet of 10 new Nissan LEAF electric cars, the largest order of the vehicle in Australia. The council has also invested in bicycle infrastructure, and cycling trips have increased by 113% across Sydney's inner-city since March 2010, with approximately 2,000 bikes passing through top peak-hour intersections on an average weekday. According to the City of Sydney Act 1988 (NSW), the Central Sydney Traffic and Transport Committee was established in 2012 to provide effective transport management in the Sydney CBD area, which is governed by Transport for NSW and the City of Sydney Council. Moreover, the Central Sydney Planning Committee is constituted by the Act to decide and approve applications of major development in the City of Sydney that cost more than 50 million dollars. These committees consider the needs of construction and development and make recommendations according to the current condition of the delegated area following the legal provisions in the City of Sydney Act. With the support of legislation, it is convenient for the council to manage the development of transport, traffic, environment and properties in the ecosystem. More recently, a \$47.5 million funding package for local companies, creative industries and the community has been endorsed by the City of Sydney Council in reaction to the coronavirus pandemic (Study NSW, 2021). This suggests that new grants, donations and services will be provided for local companies and organisations who suffered damage and loss due to COVID-19.

1.2 Transportation

The evolution of transport is a milestone for the City of Sydney local government area to promote tourism and businesses in the entrepreneurial ecosystem. Transport is an essential part to create and build an entrepreneurial ecosystem as the convenient transport attracts tourists to stay and retains talents for working in the ecosystem area. Sydney has built three terminal stations of the railway system that are all located in the City of Sydney area. The first and second terminal stations were Redfern station, which was inconvenient for passengers to move around the city area. Therefore, the third terminal station was established in 1906 which is called the Central station, located one block closer to Sydney city (Wotherspoon, 2008). The establishment of Central station has fostered the development of retail stores and businesses around the station. Besides trains, other transport services such as bus and light rail are

operating in the City of Sydney area to help people to commute and travel conveniently with less time compared with private vehicles. With the increasing number of private cars on the road, traffic jams and parking problems have become common for people to drive in the city. The City of Sydney Council is responsible for managing the parking zones within the City of Sydney area. The application for parking permits, parking metres and reports of parking issues are services provided by the council to reduce traffic and parking problems in the city (City of Sydney, n.d.). It is still a challenge for the council to manage and monitor the transport and parking in the designated area. Through the technology innovation for the improvement of transport services, it will be better for people to travel and work within the City of Sydney ecosystem.

1.3 Education

The changes in the education sector in the City of Sydney area have contributed to popularising knowledge and skills, cultivating talents and developing entrepreneurial thinking for students. Universities and other education institutions such as University of Sydney and University of Technology Sydney are the main stakeholders to cooperate with industry partners and government agencies within the entrepreneurial ecosystem. For example, UTS's Institute for Sustainable Future has collaborated with Transport for NSW to support student projects that would improve public transport service. New innovations and technologies will be generated by university students to help to solve transportation problems. To spread the importance of entrepreneurship in the community, Sydney School of Entrepreneurship (SSE, 2021) was established in 2016 with a collaboration with eleven universities and TAFE in NSW. The SSE is the first government-initiated school to enhance innovative thinking and entrepreneurial skills across various disciplines, encouraging students to be entrepreneurs and start-ups in the future. This has shaped the entrepreneurial ecosystem into its current state because education providers start to focus on the knowledge transfer of innovative thinking and entrepreneurship to promote the growth and development of entrepreneurs.

2 Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Map

2.1 Important Ecosystem Factors

2.1.1 Leadership & Council

The importance of leadership and council is to provide regulatory governance fundamental for the entrepreneurial ecosystem. The City of Sydney Council is a vital stakeholder as it is the local government council responsible for numerous services that allow the community to move.

Inclusive of transport, construction, business trading, family services etc. that facilitate the community to prosper.

Linked off the City of Sydney Council, libraries are an important and meaningful part of the ecosystem. It provides helpful information for research and development and to learn new skills. In addition to enabling opportunities for individuals to connect with resources and other people in their community.

2.1.2 Education

Educational institutions are a vital actor within the ecosystem. Public research Universities within the City of Sydney and Tafe NSW are crucial providers of education and training for the community to develop and contribute to their current and future ecosystem. Within the universities, programs are provided, UTS start-ups aim to assist and inspire entrepreneurship within the University, administering skills, knowledge, and confidence to strengthen and guide the individual's journey within the ecosystem.

Further, University of Sydney offers the Jacaranda Flame Student Consulting Program. The program gives students the opportunity to solve real engineering problems with partners, such as Transport for NSW. The collaboration between the University of Sydney and Transport for NSW gathers talent specialising in the technology and engineering industry to deliver innovative solutions to their complex problems. Strengthening the link between talent, innovation and the future of transport within Sydney, crucial for the development of the ecosystem.

2.1.3 Talent & Knowledge

For an ecosystem to develop and succeed, it is critical to retain talent and knowledge through educational institutions and co-working spaces such as Sydney Start-up Hub. They are the foundation of producing current and future talent. To improve the City of Sydney precinct and innovate the transport sector further sustainably.

2.1.4 Support Services

Support services have a pivotal role within the community. Whether they are run by the local government or by a non-government organisation, they provide access to a combination of different services such as information, advice, and financial help. Especially relevant across the entrepreneurial process, as through failure individuals will grow and succeed, support networks are essential when suffering from emotions like stress. Increased community support and community participation will provide a greater sense of connectedness to sustain the community and help it thrive.

2.1.5 Sustainability

Innovation is a crucial aspect for Transport for NSW to ensure their infrastructure and services within the City of Sydney are sustainable. Gathering an individual's talent, knowledge, and experience to propose new strategies for future courses of action. With individual's and their knowledge, research and development and focusing on what is practical and efficient for the City of Sydney community, Transport for NSW can continue to focus on a more sustainable future.

2.1.6 Networks/Culture & Infrastructure

The implementation of multiple start-up hubs and accelerators within the City of Sydney region has significantly grown. The Transport Digital Accelerator was established at the Sydney Start-up Hub to introduce a team within Transport for NSW to provide solutions and strategies to current and arising challenges. Another is Transport for NSW Research Hub, a platform that allows collaboration between academics, government agencies and industry partners to solve complex problems and encourage innovation within the Transport sector.

Increased collaboration between start-up hubs, their co-working spaces and accelerators has and will continue to improve an individual's ability to network outside of their groups. Sydney school of

entrepreneurship, Sydney start-up hub and more all provide public co-working spaces to collaborate with other individuals, mentors, advisors that could significantly impact their growth and accelerate their knowledge and development of projects.

2.1.7 Finance

Financing options within Sydney have become more available over the past five years. The government provides grants and sponsorships for new businesses that will provide benefits inclusive of supporting the economy, encouraging environmental sustainability, and developing the community. Further entrepreneurs have access to extra assistance to grow their business in their local community. The grants and sponsorships available have significantly encouraged and allowed individuals to start their businesses, to support the community in becoming more economically and environmentally sustainable. Finance options are paramount for an entrepreneurial ecosystem. In previous years, entrepreneurs had taken their talent and built their success stories in the United States, which is not beneficial for the City of Sydney entrepreneurial ecosystem.

3 Leverage Proposal

3.1 Vision for Proposal

Our vision is to create a sustained and flourishing collaboration between Tech Central and Transport NSW, two major stakeholders in our Entrepreneurial Ecosystem, to promote interconnectedness between a government body and an up and coming innovation and technology hub. The aim is to innovate Transport NSW by sourcing from the wealth of knowledge that is available in the present Tech Central hub. This will require the implementation of a diverse team within the heart of Tech Central that will include STEM research students, entrepreneurs and Transport NSW officials to tackle the biggest City of Sydney's transport problems. The team within Tech Central will operate on behalf of Transport NSW and shall consequently be funded by the government. The connection between the two stakeholders will foster open lines of communication and utilise a co-creation and a communal approach to enable continued growth in the transport sector.

3.2 Opportunities for development in the EE

Transport NSW's dedicated team will efficiently work to solve complex problems within Tech Central as it has door to door access to untapped resources and poses great potential for growth.

Currently there are various opportunities which are available to those entrepreneurs who are currently working in the Tech Central space, most of which are specific and narrow, and ultimately leave individuals with the task of finding the right industry to partner with. Transport NSW however has a multitude of unique issues that they intend to solve through sourcing ideas from unique perspectives and industries. Therefore, Transport NSW is impartial to the entrepreneurs that wish to work and innovate alongside them. While we have identified the stakeholders that will collaborate in the ecosystem, it is important to also note that the City of Sydney Council will be responsible for pulling the levers and allowing the proposal to operate efficiently and smoothly.

3.3 Relevant Stakeholder Interactions

In order for our leverage proposal to be functional and efficacious, relevant stakeholders in the entrepreneurial ecosystem need to be active participants throughout the proposal's development and solidification. As John Nelson stated (Appendix 1), an entrepreneurial ecosystem is namely characterised by firm stakeholder relationships. The nature of the plan greatly relies upon the relationships and connectivity between involved parties - thus, a clear outline and linkage between stakeholders needs to be established.

3.3.1 Transport NSW

Transport NSW is the most influential, authoritative stakeholder in the proposal. The government agency serves the purpose of three functions: creation, development and monitoring of the Tech Central-based

team. Firstly, without the approval and cooperation of Transport NSW, the proposal lacks the foundation to have a significant, legitimate impact on the given ecosystem.

The government entity will need to facilitate the team in: acquiring sufficient resources, setting out appropriate plans and directing the overall focus of the collective. Furthermore, following the creation of the collaborative entity, Transport NSW needs to be extensively involved in the development stage of the initiative. This particular phase of the proposal requires most involvement on behalf of Transport NSW due to the volatility of the development stage - where groups/teams are subjected to high probabilities of adversity and ultimately, failure. Lastly, monitoring the progress of the proposal is essential in successfully meeting set-out objectives.

Whilst the burden of responsibility at this stage doesn't solely fall on Transport NSW, the entity still needs to continuously examine the operations of the collaborative team. As it can be noted, Transport NSW is a vital stakeholder in our proposal.

3.3.2 Entrepreneurs

Entrepreneurs are the most active, operative and contributive stakeholders in the proposal. Their main function is fairly uncomplicated; they work as a collective with the aim to apply their knowledge and expertise in the creation of innovations for Transport NSW. Entrepreneurs will conduct their operations throughout dedicated facilities within Tech Central; using the engaging environment as a way to inspire and breed innovation. The day-to-day operations/functions of entrepreneurs are to: maintain contact with Transport NSW, collaboratively work towards innovative solutions and act as a beacon of hope for future entrepreneurs attempting to enter the ecosystem.

- Communicating with Transport NSW is pivotal in ensuring that correct objectives are being put forth and achieved.
- Collaborative work with the goal of developing innovations is the main focus of the group.
- Utilising the collective as evidence to aspiring entrepreneurs is important in showcasing that the transport industry is a prime environment for innovation.

Thus, entrepreneurs that are part of the proposed group, are an essential stakeholder in our proposal.

3.3.3 STEM Students

Similarly to entrepreneurs, STEM students are also one of the more proactive and engaged stakeholders in our proposal. Whilst the entrepreneurs are the main driving force of the project, STEM students are the potential future entrepreneurs in the Tech Central-based group. In the initial phases of our proposal, STEM students will be on-floor, viewing the operations of the team - gaining valuable insights and knowledge of the ecosystem. Once the project enters the development/maintenance phase (i.e. there's stability and the absence of turbulence), STEM students will be presented with the opportunity to actively work and engage with the team. This will allow for the individuals to grow into the ecosystem - rather than, for the lack of a better term, thrown into the deep end. In terms of attracting STEM students to the proposal, potential candidates from local universities (e.g University of Sydney, University of Technology Sydney, University of New South Wales), can register through an application to join the project.

Hence, STEM students are a vital stakeholder in our proposal.

3.3.4 Tech Central

Tech Central is a clear and straight-forward stakeholder, working in cooperation with Transport NSW, Entrepreneurs and STEM students to provide the group with facilities that'll assist in their operations. Tech Central's environment will have a dramatic impact on accessibility to various innovative resources - a major asset for start-ups operating in an intensive, valuable industry.

Thus, Tech Central is a fundamental stakeholder in our proposal.

3.4 Execution of proposal - How will it work?

As stated earlier in this proposal, we aim to have a dedicated team of entrepreneurs and STEM students in TechCentral who will work on behalf of Transport NSW to solve complex problems and increase the transport sector's growth. For this plan to be executed, we need willing entrepreneurs and STEM students who will want to be part of that team. Entrepreneurs and STEM students will benefit from this plan as they would be exposed to specific transport problems that they may not have otherwise been exposed to. They

may be able to apply their current solutions to or have the opportunity to adapt their solutions to these problems.

As our plan relies on having willing entrepreneurs to participate, as a group, we approached the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship (SSE) as we intend them to be our main source of innovation. We approached the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship to gain insight into their knowledge about the transport sector, Transport NSW, and if some of their entrepreneurs would be willing to be part of the team. Entrepreneurs from the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship are key assets for the execution of our plan as their entrepreneurial mindset will not only allow them to solve problems that will help the NSW transport sector but also other state and territories transport sectors, as each state and territory, would have similar problems to NSW. That is, they can not only contribute their technical solutions but also apply their way of thinking.

Further, entrepreneurs from the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship are likely to have connections with other start-ups, incubators, and accelerators in a similar field or a field that could help them solve the problems. They are key parts of the ecosystem that could expand the sources of ideas and solutions to their networks

3.5 Projections of the EE

To ensure the sustainable development of the ecosystem, cooperation between the government and the technology development centre is necessary. The goal of Tech Central is to create more resources. Its core comprises multiple cultures, including STEM researchers, and these students have the development potential and potential candidates to become innovative entrepreneurs. As a collective unit, entrepreneurs and transport NSW have shared goals by establishing sustainable development cooperation to promote the connection between the government and emerging innovation and technology centres.

In terms of entrepreneurship, the exercises established by the Entrepreneurship Academy and the Transportation Department can provide more job opportunities for the social ecosystem. In addition, the

college can also help start-ups, incubators and accelerators to establish connections for fledgling entrepreneurs in solving problem areas. Besides, the involvement of the Sydney local council will also keep the competition among entrepreneurs fair. Therefore, Transport NSW actively cooperates with multi-level stakeholders to find more innovative policies to face the rapid urbanisation development.

References

- Australian Bureau of Statistics. (2021). Retrieved 4 July 2021, from <https://www.abs.gov.au/>
- INTERVIEW: Michael Kaine - 2 April 2020 - David and Will - Omny.fm. (2021). Retrieved 4 July 2021, from <https://omny.fm/shows/david-and-will/interview-michael-kaine-2-april-2020> City of Sydney Act 1988 (NSW).
- City of Sydney. (2020, April 9). The city at a glance. City of Sydney. <https://www.cityofsydney.nsw.gov.au/guides/city-at-a-glance>
- City of Sydney. (n.d.). Transport & parking. <https://www.cityofsydney.nsw.gov.au/transport-parking>
- NSW Government. (2021). The future of transport is in NSW. Invest NSW. <https://invest.nsw.gov.au/sector-opportunities/transport>
- Our Leadership - Transport Workers' Union NSW. (2021). Retrieved 4 July 2021, from <https://twunsw.org.au/our-leadership/>
- Study NSW. (2021). Government services and support. <https://www.study.sydney/student-welfare/government-services-and-support>
- SSE. (2021). Education Partners. <https://sse.edu.au/who-we-are/universities-and-tafe>
- Transport for NSW. (2021). Future Transport Technology. <https://future.transport.nsw.gov.au/technology>
- Wotherspoon, G. (2008). Transport. The Dictionary of Sydney. <https://dictionaryofsydney.org/entry/transport>

uts.edu.au/about/td-school

CONNECT WITH US

[UTS.TDschool](https://www.facebook.com/UTS.TDschool)

[utstdschool](https://www.instagram.com/utstdschool)

[UTSTDSchool](https://twitter.com/UTSTDSchool)